

Assessing equity and mitigation outcomes in multiple degrowth pathways

Abstract

We use a socially and environmentally extended input–output model to explore 162 global degrowth pathways. While all scenarios assume deliberate reductions in consumption by richer households they differ in the overall scale and pace of reduction, the degree of convergence between social classes and regions, and the extent of technological, structural, and behavioral change. The scenarios produce a wide range of climate outcomes, with global mean temperature increases of 2.56 – 4.49 °C above preindustrial levels. These differences in mitigation outcomes are accompanied by large variations in global output, land use, and per capita consumption. Our findings show that simply downscaling existing economic structures cannot achieve climate targets. Effective and equitable mitigation instead requires deep convergence in consumption towards low levels worldwide, coupled with transformative socio-technological changes in production systems. These results highlight the importance of integrating social equity and systemic innovation into pathways for sustainable post-growth futures.

Display items

Dimension () State []	Scale of degrowth (1)	Pace (2)	Convergence (3)	Electricity mix (4)	Factor intensity (5)	Agricultural production (6)	Diet (7)
[1]	Moderate (11000 €)	Fast (to 2040)	Complete	No changes	Lower [higher] labor [energy] intensity	Conventional	Meat- based
[2]	Weak (15400 €)	Moderate (to 2060)	Interregional	100% renewable	Higher [lower] labor [energy] intensity	Organic	Plant- based
[3]	Strong (6600 €)	Slow (to 2100)	Intraregional	Combination of dimensions and states generates scenario pathways, e.g. 1111111, 1211111, ..., 3332222.			

Table 1: Overview of DG scenario dimensions and possible states of the dimensions.

Figure 1: Temperature change ($^{\circ}\text{C}$, reference year 1850) for all simulated scenarios. a) all pathways. b) pathways leading to the highest and the lowest temperature outcome in 2100. c) colored: pathways with moderate scale of DG. d) colored: pathways with weak scale of DG. e) colored: pathways with strong scale of DG. f) colored: pathways with fast pace of convergence. g) colored: pathways with moderate pace of convergence. h) colored: pathways with slow pace of convergence. i) colored: pathways with complete convergence. j) colored: pathways with interregional convergence. k) colored: pathways with intraregional convergence. l) colored: pathways without policies. m) colored: pathways with renewable electricity policy. n) colored: pathways with increased labor intensity policy. o) colored: pathways with

organic agriculture policy. p) colored: pathways with plant-based diet policy. q) colored: pathways with all policies applied.

Figure 2: Annual world output (trillion €). Colored: output pathways with a) moderate scale of DG. b) moderate scale and complete convergence. c) moderate scale and interregional convergence. d) moderate scale and intraregional convergence. e) weak scale of DG. f) weak scale and complete convergence. g) weak scale and interregional convergence. h) weak scale and intraregional convergence. i) strong scale of DG. j) strong scale and complete convergence. k) strong scale and interregional convergence. l) strong scale and intraregional convergence.

Figure 3: Consumption pathways ($\text{€ person}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$) under strong, moderate and weak DG for the richest 20% of the Center (T20C) (purple) and the poorest 30% of the Periphery (B30P) (brown) corresponding to lower (green) (a-h) and higher (yellow) (i-t) temperature changes at the end of the century. a) T20C consumption for fast and complete convergence (purple). b) B30P consumption for fast and complete convergence (brown). c) T20C consumption for slow and complete convergence (purple). d) B30P consumption for slow and complete convergence (brown). e) T20C consumption for slow and interregional convergence (purple). f) B30P consumption for slow and interregional convergence (brown). g) T20C consumption for slow and intraregional convergence (purple). h) B30P consumption for slow and intraregional convergence (brown). i) T20C consumption for fast and complete convergence (purple). j) B30P consumption for fast and complete convergence (brown). k) T20C consumption for fast and interregional convergence (purple). l) B30P consumption for fast and interregional convergence (brown). m) T20C consumption for fast and intraregional convergence (purple). n) B30P consumption for fast and intraregional convergence (brown). o) T20C consumption for slow and complete convergence (purple). p) B30P consumption for slow and complete convergence (brown). q) T20C consumption for slow and interregional convergence (purple). r) B30P consumption for slow and interregional convergence (brown). s) T20C consumption for slow and intraregional convergence (purple). t) B30P consumption for slow and intraregional convergence (brown).

Figure 4: Use of cropland and pastures (mio. km²). Pathways with a) no policies and fast convergence (until 2040). b) organic agriculture policy and fast convergence. c) plant-based diet policy and fast convergence. d) all policies and fast convergence. e) no policies and slow convergence (until 2100). f) organic agriculture policy and fast convergence. g) plant-based diet policy and fast convergence. h) all policies and fast convergence. White-colored points: All simulated land use pathways.

Main

Existing climate mitigation scenarios compatible with the Paris Agreement often rely heavily on large-scale deployment of negative emissions technologies (NETs) that enable scenarios with both high consumption growth and high climate mitigation [1], [2]. Those scenarios have attracted criticism for violating principles of precaution and responsibility, given the unresolved technical, environmental, and social challenges of deploying NETs at the required scale [3], [4]. In light of these concerns, strategies that go beyond technological solutions and rather focus on behavioral changes, ways of life and consumption patterns have increasingly gained attention [5], [6], [7].

Degrowth (DG), understood as the intentional downscaling of production and consumption in high-income countries to reduce environmental pressures and improve equity and well-being, has emerged as one such strategy [8], [9]. In recent years, the concept has gained visibility in academic research civil society, and policymaking, with some members of the European Parliament expressing radical positions with regard to sustainability, including support for post-growth and eco-socialism [10], [11]. This development parallels a growing body of modeling work on basic human needs and resource distribution [12], [13], post-growth and DG transitions [14], [15], [16], [17], as well as analyses of demand-side solutions [18], [19].

However, despite this progress, degrowth futures are characterized by considerable uncertainties, including the scale of reduction required, the pace of the transition, and the degree of convergence between high- and low-income countries. Quantitative modeling work on DG is still relatively scarce [20], reflected in the underrepresentation of low energy and material demand scenarios in the IPCC scenario database [21] and the absence of post-growth in the

original shared socio-economic pathways (SSP) and the resulting modeling studies [22], [23]. Traditional modeling work based on integrated assessment models (IAMs) suffers from a pro-growth bias stemming from both the models' structure and variables, and from modeling practices striving to create shared baselines among different IAMs [24]. Although some IAMs have been adapted to represent degrowing economies [17], [25] and ecological macroeconomic models have been constructed to model post-growth pathways [26], [27], DG and post-growth modeling studies often use different assumptions, system boundaries, and geographic scopes, making results difficult to compare [14]. Consequently, it remains unclear under which conditions DG could achieve climate targets while avoiding adverse impacts on living standards, or whether there is a trade-off between mitigation and poverty alleviation [13], [28].

Here, we address this gap by constructing 162 DG scenarios simulated with the IAM MORDRED. All scenarios assume deliberate consumption reductions among richer households but differ in the overall scale and pace of reduction, the degree of convergence across income groups, and the extent of technological, structural, and behavioral change. Using a single, integrated modelling framework enables systematic comparison of the scenarios in terms of climate outcomes and key socio-environmental variables, including global output, land use, and per capita consumption. This comprehensive scenario set allows us to evaluate the individual and combined effects of different DG dimensions. Our results demonstrate that simulating DG within IAMs can inform the design of equitable and precautionary climate strategies.

Results

Scenario design

We define seven dimensions linked to a DG transition: the target per capita consumption level, or scale of DG which can range between €6,600 and €15,400 (1); the pace of consumption convergence, or pace of DG i.e. convergence until 2040, 2060 or 2100 (2); the degree of convergence, which can be complete or incomplete (3); the electricity mix that can be partially or fully renewable (4); factor intensities of production i.e. a possible increase in labor intensity linked to a decrease in energy intensity (5); agricultural production techniques (organic or conventional) (6); and the composition of the human diet (meat- or plant-based) (7). The 162 pathways are constructed by varying the states of the seven dimensions across the scenarios. Table 1 summarizes the scenario design which is explained in detail in the Methods section. S1 Supplementary Information (SI) lists all scenarios with their characteristics.

Climate change mitigation under DG

Figure 1 presents projected changes in global average temperature (°C) relative to the pre-industrial period across all simulated DG scenarios. The variance is considerable: while global average temperature rises by more than 400% relative to initial values in the highest-emission scenarios, it increases by less than 230% in the lowest-emission pathways. The worst-performing scenario (pathway 2132111) reaches 4.48 °C in 2100, far beyond 'safe and just' thresholds [29] while even the best-performing pathway (3312222) is linked to an increase of 2.56 °C (Figure 1b). Accordingly, none of the 162 DG pathways achieves the 1.5 °C or 2 °C climate target, and only 25 limit warming to 3.2 °C or below. These findings are contextualized further in the Discussion section.

Although no single DG dimension determines climate outcomes, differences among pathways can be partially explained by how individual dimensions are set.

Although no single DG dimension fully determines climate outcomes, differences among pathways can be partially explained by how scale, pace, and degree of convergence are implemented. First, scenarios with a strong DG scale—defined as a per-capita consumption target of €6,600 year⁻¹ for the middle class of the semiperiphery—consistently achieve better climate outcomes than those with moderate (€11,000) or weak (€15,400) targets (Figure 1c-e). Temperature ranges are [2.56–4.27 °C] for ‘strong’ DG, [3.01–4.48 °C] for ‘moderate’ DG, and [3.33–4.49 °C] for ‘weak’ DG. This finding supports the notion of a trade-off between higher consumption levels and climate safety, demonstrating that reducing resource use in richer households is critical for limiting warming.

Second, the pace of convergence between classes and regions plays an important but nuanced role. Scenarios with slower convergence generally perform better than those with faster convergence (Figure 1f-h). Temperature ranges are [2.56–4.39 °C] for convergence by 2100, [2.66–4.49 °C] by 2060, and [2.7–4.49 °C] by 2040. Contrary to the hypothesis that faster convergence improves climate outcomes, we find that faster convergence increases the rate of consumption growth among poorer households, whose increasing demand partially offsets the reduction in consumption by richer households. Slower convergence reduces total demand and production over the century, moderating emissions. This finding illustrates a tension between equity in consumption and climate outcomes: faster convergence enhances social equality more quickly, but may exacerbate cumulative emissions if it triggers rapid demand growth.

Third, the degree of convergence matters substantially. Complete convergence yields a temperature range of [2.56–4.35 °C], outperforming both interregional ([3.11–4.49 °C]) and intraregional ([3.0–4.49 °C]) convergence scenarios (Figure 1i-k). In inter- and intraregional scenarios, inequality between the richest and poorest households or regions is reduced to a 3:1 ratio, i.e. inequality drops consistently in spite of the absence of full convergence. Thus, maintaining current inequality levels in these partial-convergence pathways would result in even less climate mitigation. These results indicate that convergence does not involve a trade-off between equity and climate mitigation, but rather fosters both objectives.

Comparing the three dimensions, scale and degree of convergence emerge as slightly more influential in shaping climate outcomes than the pace of convergence. Especially strong DG and complete convergence seem to have the potential to significantly limit global warming during the 21st century, suggesting that both cutting the per-capita consumption of richer households and reducing inequality are essential for mitigation. The pace of convergence, while secondary, modulates the timing and cumulative effect of demand shifts across the global population.

Policy interventions exhibit diverse unexpected effects and strong context dependency (Figure 1.l-q). The shift to 100% renewable electricity appears in both the best- and worst-performing pathways, highlighting strong context dependency as they can both support cleaner energy production under low consumption and improve the efficiency of the total energy system as fossil resources become more costly to access, thus, prolonging the reproductive capacity of a fossil-fuel based energy infrastructure. Temperature *ceteris paribus* increases slowest when all policies are implemented. Interestingly, the plant-based diet policy slightly accelerates warming early in the century: Improvements in land-use efficiency initially do not occur fast enough to satisfy total desired consumption demand but since dietary shifts ease land constraints, a higher share of demanded consumption can be fulfilled. Thus, global output rises faster and emissions increase temporarily. Changes in factor intensities modestly improve outcomes (–0.1 °C between best-performing factor-intensity and no-policy scenarios), while the organic agriculture

policy shows a negligible effect (-0.000004 °C), likely due to the relatively simplistic implementation of the policy in the model (see Methods).

Of the 25 lower-temperature pathways, 22 feature strong DG, 21 complete convergence, 13 slow convergence (to 2100), and 11 a switch to renewables (alone or with other policies). The best scenario without explicit DG policies combines slow, complete convergence to a low consumption level and reaches 2.8 °C in 2100.

Overall, the findings demonstrate that climate mitigation under DG depends on the interplay of consumption reductions, convergence dynamics, and context-specific policies, highlighting the need to consider social equity, consumption patterns, and structural policies together when designing DG pathways.

Development of total output

The DG scenarios produce a wide range of global output trajectories, driven primarily by demographic trends, target consumption levels, the availability of input factors and resources, and specific scenario characteristics. In the early years of the simulation, total output rises in all scenarios, reflecting limited convergence and a continuous increase in the consumption of the poorest households (B30P). From 2030 onward, differences in output dynamics are mainly determined by the scale of DG and the degree of convergence.

Under strong DG, low consumption targets that affect a large share of the global population cause world output to peak earlier and at lower levels (Figure 2.i). In contrast, scenarios in which household consumption converges toward higher levels display prolonged and stronger growth, reaching higher output peaks (Figure 2.a, e). Differences between moderate and weak DG are comparatively minor, while the contrast between strong DG and the other two variants is pronounced. Complete convergence leads to earlier and lower peaks than partial convergence, with inter- and intraregional convergence showing similar overall behavior, though interregional convergence typically produces slightly higher peaks.

A 'moderate' scale of DG with complete convergence (Figure 2.b) leads to a first peak and subsequent moderate decline in the 2030s, followed by renewed growth as global convergence progresses. The rate of increase depends primarily on the pace of convergence: faster convergence yields faster growth, with output peaking between 2060 and 2070 at more than twice its initial level. Under moderate DG with inter- or intraregional convergence (Figure 2.c-d), output peaks between two and four times the initial value, depending on the convergence pace.

A 'weak' scale of DG exhibits similar qualitative patterns, although complete convergence (Figure 2.f) produces longer and higher output growth, followed by pronounced late-century declines not observed under moderate DG (Figure 2.b). In contrast, strong DG produces sharp declines only in the final decade, particularly under interregional convergence (Figure 2.k). Strong DG combined with complete convergence leads to final output levels comparable to initial output (in 2100: $[0.99 - 1.1]$ x initial output) (Figure 2.j) while strong DG combined with intraregional convergence yields output levels 1.5-1.7 x initial output.

In scenarios lacking strong DG or complete convergence, output contracts sharply toward the end of the century due to fossil resource depletion. In 63 of 162 scenarios, global output in 2100 is more than 20 % below its initial level. These dynamics are driven by the depletion of fossil reserves and critically depend on the assumption of low fossil resource accessibility. Policies

delay but do not prevent resource scarcity; the full policy set is most effective, followed by factor-intensity change, expansion of renewable electricity, and organic agriculture.

Hence, surprisingly, even persistent DG among richer households does not necessarily reduce world output. Instead, output dynamics are shaped by the interaction between the scale of DG, convergence dynamics, and resource availability. Conversely, weak DG and incomplete convergence can produce unintended and steep output reductions under insufficient fossil fuel substitution once reserves are depleted. These findings highlight that maintaining global output under DG conditions requires not only equitable consumption convergence but also technological and structural transitions beyond the greening of the electricity mix.

Development of household consumption

Simulation results cover consumption pathways for all nine household types pertaining to the global economy, i.e. the top 20%, the bottom 30% and the remaining middle 50% of all high-income countries ('Center'), all upper-middle income countries ('Semiperiphery') and all lower- and low income countries ('Periphery'): T20C, B30C, M50C, T20S, B30S, M50S, T20P, B30P and M50P. Here, we focus on the 'extreme' cases of the T20C and B30P households, while results for the other household types are visualized in S3 of the SI.

Figure 3.a-h displays consumption pathways for low-emission scenarios (≤ 3.2 °C), while Figure 3.i-t shows consumption pathways of high-emission scenarios. Per-capita consumption of T20C ranges between €19,800 and €6,600 year⁻¹ under strong DG, corresponding to a reduction of 53–84 % compared to the initial level. The B30P group, by contrast, experiences a substantial increase, reaching €6,600–11,000 year⁻¹—7 to 12 times its initial consumption.

Higher-emission scenarios are more numerous and often deviate from the exogenously specified convergence targets. Under moderate or weak DG with fast and complete convergence, T20C and B30P consumption levels meet around 2040 but remain below the target due to insufficient land-intensity improvements. Only in later decades, as efficiency increases, do consumption targets become attainable (Figure 3.i-j). Fast and interregional convergence leads to a sharp early rise in B30P consumption that later stabilizes or collapses under resource scarcity. The T20C pattern mirrors this behavior, with more pronounced late-century declines under intraregional convergence.

Slow but complete convergence yields steady decline in T20C consumption and a continuous rise for B30P, reaching €11,000–15,400 year⁻¹ by 2100 (Figure 3.o and p). In contrast, under slow inter- or intraregional convergence (Figure 3.q-t), T20C consumption remains high for most of the century before collapsing, while B30P consumption drops to much lower levels. Scenario 2332222, which retains high consumption the longest, reaches €43,000 year⁻¹ for T20C and €14,348 year⁻¹ for B30P in 2100.

Despite clear trade-offs between consumption and climate outcomes, similar temperature responses can occur across scenarios with markedly different consumption levels among the poorest households. For instance, scenario 1312222 (slow, complete convergence with all policies implemented) yields €11,000 year⁻¹ for B30P and a global warming of 3.01 °C, while scenario 3322222 (slow interregional convergence with all policies) produces €6,600 year⁻¹ for B30P and a warming of 3.11 °C.

These results highlight the central role of convergence for both equity and mitigation. Complete convergence enables sustained improvements in well-being among low-income groups while maintaining lower overall energy and material demand. In contrast, partial or delayed

convergence —whether inter- or intraregional— preserves high consumption levels among the richest households for much of the century, eventually leading to abrupt declines as resource constraints intensify.

Overall, the findings suggest that effective climate mitigation and equitable consumption outcomes depend less on absolute consumption targets and more on the speed and completeness of convergence. Even low inequality ratios can lower mitigation, indicating that sufficiency-oriented pathways with complete global convergence are essential for aligning degrowth strategies with both social and climatic goals.

Land use

Land-use dynamics for food production (cropland + grassland) vary substantially across the simulated scenario pathways (Figure 4). A slower convergence pace (to 2100) leads to stronger and more persistent reductions in land use compared to a faster convergence (to 2040), while scenarios with moderate convergence (to 2060) lie in between. Sharp declines toward the end of the century, observable in several pathways, result from collapsing output driven by fossil resource scarcity and its feedback effects on agricultural productivity and demand.

Relative to no-policy pathways (Figure 4a, e), organic agriculture increases land use, whereas plant-based diets reduce it. Under fast convergence, the lowest land-use case without policies (3111111) reaches 25 million km² in 2060, about 40% below the initial value. The best organic agriculture case (3111121) requires 28.7 million km², while the best plant-based diet case (3111112) uses 20.1 million km². When all policies are combined (3112222), total land use is about 8% lower than in the best no-policy case. Under slow convergence, these effects are more pronounced: organic agriculture occasionally increases land use, whereas plant-based diets consistently lower it.

Across all simulations, strong DG and complete convergence generally produce lower land-use outcomes, though exceptions exist. For instance, under slow convergence, scenarios combining strong DG with intraregional convergence and a plant-based diet (e.g., 3331112, 3321112) result in lower land demand than those combining strong DG with complete convergence and organic agriculture (3311121).

Overall, the differences in land-use trajectories are driven less by DG-specific land policies than by underlying land-productivity assumptions, macroeconomic developments, and a relative decline in the demand for agricultural products as consumption levels of poorer households rise. Interactions between technological efficiency, resource scarcity, and convergence speed largely determine the extent to which DG pathways reduce pressure on agricultural land. While plant-based diets reliably decrease land use, organic agriculture tends to offset some of these gains due to lower yields. Balancing sufficiency-oriented consumption changes with continued productivity improvements therefore emerges as a critical condition for achieving sustainable land-use outcomes under degrowth pathways.

Discussion

Degrowth and climate targets

Our finding that none of the DG scenarios achieves sufficient mitigation to limit global warming to 1.5 °C or 2 °C should not be understood as an indirect argument for Green Growth (GG)

approaches. To assess the performance of a DG scenario compared to a GG scenario would require a separate scenario analysis with careful scenario design and implementation in the same model to ensure comparability of results.

The relatively low mitigation effect throughout all scenario simulations can be explained by several factors. First, for methodological reasons, we make very conservative assumptions regarding energy efficiency compared to other scenarios. Our aim was to explore the effects of reducing the consumption of richer households, in combination with concrete technological changes, rather than to assess possible economy-wide future improvements in energy intensity. Second, the model reflects the growing depletion of fossil resources through an increase in the input factors of the extractive sector, which worsens energy and carbon intensity and further accelerates global warming. Last, we do not include negative emission technologies (NETs) due to concerns regarding their performance, scalability, and sustainability implications [30], [31].

It follows that DG pathways could be made compatible with climate targets if they are combined with assumptions of stronger economy-wide efficiency gains, greater availability of fossil fuels, and/or NETs. Under these conditions, DG pathways would very likely outperform GG pathways in terms of climate mitigation. Alternatively, DG pathways could be made compatible with climate targets through a complete structural reorganization of the economy resulting in changed production processes and technologies, such as 'low-tech' [32], which are very difficult to represent with models built on data from the currently existing economic structure.

Nevertheless, we would caution against unjustified overoptimism regarding DG and climate mitigation. High levels of uncertainty exist not only for possible technological and socio-economic developments but also for biophysical variables and their interactions [33], [34], [35]. Importantly, if reductions in consumption are not accompanied by deep changes in the production structure away from fossil resources, even strong DG scenarios with high energy-efficiency improvements will, in the long term, face considerable climate change and resource depletion problems.

Policy implications and feasibility

The benefits of DG policies are often linked to less pressure on land and more leisure time [36], [37]. Although this might be true in comparison to GG policies, our scenarios still depend on continued growth in labor and land productivity throughout the 21st century. In more than half of the scenarios with changes in factor intensity that increase labor and decrease energy intensity, the effect is a slowdown of the consumption growth of the poorest households, contradicting convergence goals. The higher the target consumption the greater the risk for emerging labor scarcity issues becomes. The same logic applies to land productivity improvements, and since the two policies linked to DG—a plant-based diet and a switch to organic agriculture—work in opposite directions regarding land intensity they cannot solve the problem of land scarcity.

Our simulations demonstrate that complete convergence is important to prevent ongoing poverty in the poorest households at the global scale and to achieve significant climate mitigation effects. Incomplete convergence that only addresses class or territorial inequality either depresses the consumption of poorer households or leads to continued growth in total output and emissions. However, the political feasibility of completely equalizing consumption can be doubted, given that reducing consumption inequality to a factor of 1:3 at the global level, as assumed in the scenarios of inter- and intraregional convergence, would already require unprecedented redistribution policies.

From our scenario exercise it follows that it is necessary to combine strong sufficiency and convergence in consumption with deep structural and technological changes for strong climate mitigation. Consequently, strategies of sufficiency and resource equality should be seen as complementary, not contradictory, to strategies promoting socio-technological change.

This raises critical questions about the institutional conditions that could simultaneously sustain dynamic technological progress and reduce consumption and inequality.

Methods

Model

For our scenario analysis, we use MORDRED (*Model of Resource Distribution and Resilient Economic Development*), an Integrated Assessment Model for which extensive documentation is provided in Lauer & Llases [38]. Therefore, in the following, we only provide a short summary of the model, focusing on the variables most relevant to the analysis conducted.

MORDRED was built with the intention of simulating scenarios of non-linear economic development that depart from the assumption of continued growth in world output. This is achieved by endogenizing certain variables whose development is often determined exogenously, notably demographic developments and economic output. The model consists of several modules that are coupled through various feedback relationships: Population, Economy, Labor, Energy, Land, Climate, and Environmental Stressors. The main data sources for the calibration of the model are the environmentally and socially extended IO tables from Exiobase3 for the year 2019 [39], UN population data for 2020 [40], consumption inequality data for 2014 from the GCIP database [41], climate and emission-related variables from the IPCC WGI [42] and fossil resource estimates from BGR [43].

The world population is divided into a minority that is assumed to live partially or completely outside the global economy and a majority assumed to be fully integrated into the world economy. The population pertaining to the global economy is divided into three world regions and three household types in each region. The world region 'Center' (C) covers all high-income countries; the world region 'Semiperiphery' (S) includes all upper-middle-income countries; and the world region 'Periphery' (P) includes all lower-middle- and low-income countries. In every region, the richest 20% constitute the T20 (Top 20) household type, the poorest 30% the B30 (Bottom 30) household type, and the remaining middle 50% the M50 (Middle 50) household type. Thus, the nine household types in MORDRED are: T20C, M50C, B30C, T20S, M50S, B30S, T20P, M50P, and B30P.

The economic core of MORDRED is a global input-output model with 25 sectors constructed by aggregating product-based Exiobase3 data. This level of aggregation allows model users to simulate environmental and economic policies that target food-related, industry-related, and service-related activities, as well as different energy sectors.

The desired total output of the world economy, which depends on the respective scenario, is the sum of sectoral output calculated with the Leontief matrix L and the desired final demand for every sector (1). The desired final demand by sector is the sum of the desired gross fixed capital formation ($GFCF_s$), the desired government consumption (G_s) and the desired household consumption (hh_s) by sector. Both desired GFCF and desired government consumption depend on the desired sectoral consumption of households. The latter depends on population size, consumption vectors whose composition varies with the level of per capita consumption, and the desired rate of consumption growth.

$$X = \sum_{s=1}^{25} L_{s,s} * (G_s + hh_s + GFCF_s) \quad (2)$$

For our simulation exercise, we used MORDRED 1.1.4. The most significant difference from the base version is the use of inequality factors ($IQ_{r,c:peri,B30t}$) to influence the evolution of consumption pathways of the different household types. These factors exogenously determine the consumption inequality ratio between a certain household type and the poorest household type (B30P) (2).

Based on scale, pace, and convergence, the necessary growth rate of the B30P household type to reach the target value in the respective year is calculated and set as an exogenous model input (3).

$$IQ_{r,c:peri,B30P_t} = \frac{c_{r,c_t}}{c_{B30P_t}} \quad (2)$$

$$g_{B30P} = e^{\frac{\ln\left(\frac{c_{B30P_{2019}}}{c_{B30P_{20xx}target}}\right)}{20xx-2019}} - 1 \quad (3)$$

The desired consumption pathways of the other household types are calculated by multiplying the desired per capita consumption of the B30P household type by the respective inequality factors.

In MORDRED, the desired output is only produced if all necessary input factors for the sectoral economic processes are available in the required quantity. These input factors include intermediate products, labor, different types of land, and different types of resources. Labor supply is calculated based on the population module, while land and (energy) resource availability are calculated in the respective modules. Shortages in one input factor are sufficient to slow down and reverse economic growth due to the standard input-output assumption of zero substitutability between different types of inputs. However, this assumption is softened by the very broad input categories that exist in the model. For example, the input category 'fossil fuels' implies complete substitutability between different types of fossil fuels, and the input category 'labor' implies complete substitutability between different types of workers, i.e., there is no differentiation according to skills. Likewise, the model makes optimistic assumptions regarding the convertibility of different land types; for example, forest land can always be converted into agriculturally used land.

If desired final demand is higher than what can be produced with the available production factors, the consumption of all household types is reduced to maintain the exogenously specified inequality ratios between household types.

The climate module, which is an adapted and actualized version of the climate module contained in the IAM WILLIAM [44], calculates the global average temperature change (ΔT) (6), driven by emissions of different greenhouse gases generated in the Environmental Stressors module. CO₂ emissions are calculated as the sum of emissions from fossil fuel combustion, land-use change, and other CO₂ sources (4). Emissions for greenhouse gases other than CO₂ are calculated based on emission intensities (5).

$$Em_{CO_2_t} = \sum_{i=1}^3 PE_i \cdot Int_{CO_2_i} + forest\ land\ reduction * Int_{CO_2_t} + \sum_{s=1}^{25} Int_{CO_2_{s_t}} * x_{s_t} \quad (4)$$

$$Em_{j_t} = \sum_{s=1}^{25} Int_{j_{s_t}} * x_{s_t} \quad (5)$$

$$\Delta T = f(Em_j, Em_{CO_2}) \quad (6)$$

The total land demand for every land type is calculated using land-use intensities (7). The module compares the land demanded with the quantity of available land, which can result in land-use changes or limits to economic production.

$$Land\ demand_{l_t} = \sum_{s=1}^{25} Int_{l_{s_t}} * x_{s_{desired_t}} \quad (7)$$

MORDRED contains several feedback mechanisms that link different modules, two of which were deactivated for our scenario exercise. First, our scenario analysis does not include feedback mechanisms in the climate system resulting, for example, from permafrost thawing. Second, for our simulations, we did not include possible climate impacts on economic structure and labor. Activating the first feedback mechanism would further accelerate the pace of temperature increase, while taking into account the second feedback mechanism would likely slow down economic growth as the global average temperature increases..

Scenario dimensions

In our scenario analysis, each DG scenario is characterized by seven dimensions, of which the first three are conceptual and the last four represent policies commonly associated with DG transitions [14], [45]: 1. the per capita consumption level, indicating the scale of DG; 2. the pace of convergence in per capita consumption, indicating the velocity of DG; 3. the degree of convergence in per capita consumption; 4. the electricity mix; 5. the factor intensity of production; 6. agricultural production techniques; and 7. the composition of the human diet. Each dimension can take two or three possible states, defined according to the representational capacity of MORDRED.

1. Per capita consumption level

The reference consumption level is the annual per capita consumption of the M50S household type. Three states are possible:

- (1) *Moderate DG*: the reference per capita consumption level is set to €11,000 year⁻¹. This results in an increase in per capita consumption for all household types except the richest 70% of the population in the Center. The consumption level refers solely to household consumption and excludes government consumption and investment. However, in the model, government consumption per world region is calculated as a share of regional household consumption, and investment ultimately depends on desired consumption levels. Thus, a reduction in household consumption leads to a corresponding decline in government spending and investment.

- (2) *Weak DG*: the reference consumption level increases by 40%.
- (3) *Strong DG*: the reference consumption level decreases by 40%.

This variation allows us to explore the significance of the scale of DG in the simulations. The reference level was set relatively high to avoid scenarios with excessive poverty among a minority of households in cases of strong DG and incomplete convergence between household types.

2. Pace of convergence

The pace of convergence is determined by a target year, with three possible states:

- (1) *Fast*: convergence of consumption levels by 2040.
- (2) *Moderate*: convergence of consumption levels by 2060.
- (3) *Slow*: convergence of consumption levels by 2100.

3. Degree of convergence

DG emphasizes the reduction of both intra-country and international inequality [45] which is implemented in all simulated scenarios. However, while one-third of the scenarios feature complete convergence between household types, in the remaining cases consumption inequality is not entirely eliminated. We construct three ideal types:

- (1) *Complete convergence*: in the target year, the consumption of all household types has converged to the same level.
- (2) *Interregional convergence*: in the target year, the average per capita consumption levels of all three world regions have converged. Inequality ratios between household types within a single region decline to a maximum of 3:1 between the richest (T20) and poorest (B30) household types.
- (3) *Intraregional convergence*: in the target year, the consumption of all household types within each world region has converged to the same level. Inequality ratios between the richest (Center) and poorest (Periphery) world regions drop to a maximum of 3:1.

4. Electricity mix

This dimension represents a conceivable policy in the context of a DG transition [46], [47]. Two states are possible:

- (1) *No policy*: the share of non-renewable electricity—i.e. nuclear power and electricity generated from fossil fuels (mainly carbon)—remains at its 2019 level throughout the simulation.
- (2) *Renewable electricity policy*: the share of non-renewable electricity declines to zero by 2100 and is replaced by hydro-, wind-, and solar-based electricity.

5. Factor intensity of production

This dimension represents a potential policy and reflects the idea of structural economic change towards higher labor intensity and lower energy intensity [48]. Its model implementation is

qualitative rather than quantitative, serving to illustrate basic dynamics such as potential labor scarcity or positive climate mitigation effects.

- (1) *No policy*: capital intensity remains constant; labor intensity depends solely on the scale of DG, the degree of convergence, and the model's default assumptions regarding labor productivity developments (section 2 SI).
- (2) *Factor intensity change policy*: labor intensity increases while the energy intensity of all energy inputs decreases in selected sectors (nos. 1, 5, 7, 11, 23). Consequently, the capital-to-labor ratio declines slightly in these industries.

6. Agricultural production

Two states are defined for this dimension:

- (1) *No policy*: in the absence of an agricultural production policy, industrial agricultural production remains predominantly conventional.
- (2) *Organic agriculture policy*: this policy allows us to explore some consequences of a global shift to predominantly organic agriculture. The model implementation focuses solely on direct land-use implications and their interactions with world output and emissions growth. Furthermore, the policy applies only to land used for food production, not to forestry or energy-sector land use.

7. Diet

Like agricultural production, this dimension has a policy character, can take two states, and focuses only on direct land-use implications rather than indirect emissions or climate-related effects:

- (1) *No diet policy*: land intensities follow default model assumptions.
- (2) *Planet-based diet policy*: meat-based protein and fat intake are substituted with plant-based alternatives.

Combining all dimensions and their possible states yields a theoretical scenario space of 432 potential combinations, of which 162 pathways were simulated. Each scenario pathway is denoted by a number encoding the state of each dimension. For example, a scenario of moderate DG ((1) = [1]) with fast ((2) = [1]) and complete ((3) = [1]) convergence, no changes in the electricity mix ((4) = [1]), no additional factor-intensity changes ((5) = [1]), conventional agriculture ((6) = [1]), and a meat-based diet ((7) = [1]) is labeled 1111111.

The simulated scenarios, their characteristics, and corresponding numbers are presented in Table S1. The SI also details key boundary conditions affecting simulation outcomes. Notably, boundary conditions assume no major changes in economic structure apart from moderate electrification and energy-efficiency improvements in existing industrial processes. It is assumed that for most core products of the global economy, the majority of cost-minimizing energy-efficiency measures have already been implemented. Consequently, compared to models assuming high efficiency gains, MORDRED tends to produce higher emissions from economic growth. For this study, we retained the model's default assumption to avoid conflating climate mitigation effects arising from abstract structural changes with those from explicit reductions in consumption.

Table 2 provides an overview of the scenario implementation for the selected dimensions in the model. Given the large volume of data generated by the simulations, the results section focuses on four key outputs: climate change, total output, per capita consumption, and land use for food production. The full dataset can be made available upon request.

Dimension	State	Qualitative	Quantitative
Consumption level	Moderate DG	Target consumption (c_{target}) of €11,000 year ⁻¹ person ⁻¹ for the middle class (M50) of the Semiperiphery. This value reflects the purchasing power corresponding to a monthly budget of €917 in the Eurozone in 2019.	$c_{target_{M50S}}$
	Weak DG	The target consumption increases by 40%.	$c_{target_{M50S}} * (1 + 0.4)$
	Strong DG	The target consumption decreases by 40%.	$c_{target_{M50S}} * (1 - 0.4)$
Pace	Fast	Inequality is reflected in inequality factors ($I_{Q_{r,c:peri},B30_t}$). $I_{Q_{r,c:peri},B30_t}$ are assumed to fall until 2030 after which the reduction accelerates further to reach the target level of convergence in 2040.	$I_{Q_{r,c:peri},B30_t} =$ $\max \left\{ I_{Q_{r,c:peri},B30_{2019}} * e^{-k_{2040_{1r,c}} t}, 1 \right\}$ for $t \leq 2030$ $I_{Q_{r,c:peri},B30_t} =$ $\max \left\{ I_{Q_{r,c:peri},B30_{2030}} * e^{-k_{2040_{2r,c}} t}, 1 \right\}$ for $t > 2030$ $k_{2040_{i_{r,c}}}$ takes a value that ensures that the desired convergence level is reached in 2040.
	Moderate	$I_{Q_{r,c:peri},B30_t}$ are assumed to fall slightly until 2030 after which the decrease accelerates to reach the target level of convergence in 2060.	$I_{Q_{r,c:peri},B30_t} =$ $\max \left\{ I_{Q_{r,c:peri},B30_{2019}} * e^{-k_{2060_{1r,c}} t}, 1 \right\}$ for $t \leq 2030$ $I_{Q_{r,c:peri},B30_t} =$ $\max \left\{ I_{Q_{r,c:peri},B30_{2030}} * e^{-k_{2060_{2r,c}} t}, 1 \right\}$ for $t > 2030$

			$k_{2060i_{r,c}}$ takes a value that ensures that the desired convergence level is reached in 2060.
	Slow	$IQ_{r,c:peri.,B30_t}$ are assumed to fall slightly until 2030 after which the decrease accelerates to reach the target level of convergence in 2100.	$Q_{r,c:peri.,B30_t} = \max \{ IQ_{r,c:peri.,B30_{2019}} * e^{-k_{21001r,c}t}, 1 \}$ for $t \leq 2030$ $IQ_{r,c:peri.,B30_t} = \max \{ IQ_{r,c:peri.,B30_{2030}} * e^{-k_{21002r,c}t}, 1 \}$ for $t > 2030$ $k_{2100i_{r,c}}$ takes a value that ensures that the desired convergence level is reached in 2100.
Convergence	Complete	A complete convergence between all classes and regions is assumed.	$IQ_{r,c:peri.,B30_{target\ year}} = 1$
	Interregional	A complete convergence between regions and a partial convergence between classes is assumed (the richest classes consume three times as much as the poorest class).	$IQ_{center,T20:peri.,B30_{target\ year}} = 3$ $IQ_{semi,T20:peri.,B30_{target\ year}} = 2$ $IQ_{peri,T20:peri.,B30_{target\ year}} = 1$ $IQ_{center,M50:peri.,B30_{target\ year}} = 3$ $IQ_{semi,M50:peri.,B30_{target\ year}} = 2$ $IQ_{peri,M50:peri.,B30_{target\ year}} = 1$ $IQ_{center,B30:peri.,B30_{target\ year}} = 3$ $IQ_{semi,B30:peri.,B30_{target\ year}} = 2$
	Intraregional	A complete convergence between classes and a partial convergence between regions is assumed (the classes in the richest region consume three times as much as the classes in the poorest region).	$IQ_{center,T20:peri.,B30_{target\ year}} = 3$ $IQ_{semi,T20:peri.,B30_{target\ year}} = 3$ $IQ_{peri,T20:peri.,B30_{target\ year}} = 3$ $IQ_{center,M50:peri.,B30_{target\ year}} = 2$ $IQ_{semi,M50:peri.,B30_{target\ year}} = 2$

			$IQ_{peri,M50:peri.,B30_{target\ year}} = 2$ $IQ_{center,B30:peri.,B30_{target\ year}} = 1$ $IQ_{semi,B30:peri.,B30_{target\ year}} = 1$
Electricity mix	No changes	In the A matrix, input coefficients $IC_{s_{el},s}$ representing inputs from electricity sectors s_{el} are proportionally reduced through a process efficiency coefficient (PEC) while the relation between renewable and fossil electricity remains constant.	$IC_{s_{el}:s_{2100}} = PEC * IC_{s_{el}:s_{2019}}$ $s_{el} = \{sector\ i \mid 12 \leq i \leq 20\}$
	100% renewable	$IC_{s_{el},s}$ are reduced due to the PEC . Inputs from the nuclear and fossil electricity sector are shifted to renewable electricity sectors (solar PV, wind and hydro power) in industrial processes and for the consumption vector of final demand components (CV_{FD}).	$IC_{12:s_{2100}} = 0; IC_{13:s_{2100}} = 0$ $CV_{FD_{12}2100} = 0; CV_{FD_{13}2100} = 0$ $IC_{s_{ren}:s_{2100}} = PEC * IC_{s_{ren}:s_{2019}}$ $+ \frac{1}{3} \left(PEC (IC_{12:s_{2019}} + IC_{13:s_{2019}}) \right)$ $s_{ren} = \{14,15,17\}$ $CV_{FD_{s_{ren}2100}} = CV_{FD_{s_{ren}2019}} + \frac{1}{3}$ $* \left(CV_{FD_{12}2019} + CV_{FD_{13}2019} \right)$
Factor intensity	No additional changes	Energy intensity and labor intensity developments follow pathways specified by boundary conditions (see S2 SI).	$Labor\ intensity_s = \frac{L_s}{x_{s_{exog}}}$
	Higher labor intensity	Labor intensities specified by boundary conditions are multiplied by a labor intensification factor (LIF) that increases labor intensity between 20% and 100% for selected sectors (no. 1, 5, 7, 11, 23). Those sectors that experience an increase in labor intensity also experience a decrease in energy intensity based on the assumption of	$\frac{L_s}{x_s} = \frac{L_s}{x_{s_{exog}}} * LIF_s$ $LIF_{1,5,7,11,23} > 1$

		imperfect substitution between labor and energy through the reorganization of productive processes. Thus, the <i>PEC</i> of the respective sectors is multiplied by an Economic Structural Change (<i>ESC</i>) multiplier, defined as the ratio of the Imperfect Substitution Coefficient (<i>ISC</i>) to the <i>LIF</i> .	$ESC_{1,5,7,11,23} = \frac{ISC}{LIF_{1,5,7,11,11,23}}$ $PEC_{1,5,7,11,23} = PEC_{default} * ESC_{1,5,7,11,23}$
Agricultural production	Conventional	No changes in land intensity apart from those specified by boundary conditions.	$Land\ intensity_s = \frac{Land_s}{x_s\ exog}$
	Organic	We take the average between the yield difference per unit of output in the case of best organic practices y_{bp} and in the case of highest comparability between conventional and organic systems y_{hc} compared to conventional practices y_{con} [49] to calculate the Intensity factor for Organic agriculture (<i>IO</i>), assuming that yield differences are proportional to land productivity differences. The policy only applies to land used to produce food products which is only demanded by sector 1.	$IO = \frac{1}{\left(1 - \frac{y_{bp} + y_{hc}}{2 y_{con}}\right)}$ $\frac{Foodland}{x_1} = IO * \frac{Foodland_1}{x_1\ exog}$
Diet	Meat-based	No changes in land intensity apart from those specified by boundary conditions.	$Land\ intensity_s = \frac{Land_s}{x_s\ exog}$
	Plant-based	Based on data for the land intensity of 15 food products ($\frac{land_j}{kcal_j}$) serving as protein source [50], we constructed two diet vectors v_i that specify the share of calories covered by every food product. The meat-based diet vector contains high shares for meat-based food products while the share of meat-based products is 0 in the plant-based diet vector. With the vectors and the land intensities for all food products, the weighted land intensity μ_{i_w} is calculated. The land intensity factor for protein calorie intake (ID_{pro}) is defined as the ratio of the weighted land intensity of a plant-based diet to that of a meat-based diet. For simplicity, we assume the same difference in land intensity also for fat-based calories in the human diet. However, since	$i_1 = meat, i_2 = plant$ $\mu_{i_w} = \sum_{j=1}^{15} \frac{land}{kcal_j} * v_{j,i}$ $ID_{pro} = \frac{\mu_{2_w}}{\mu_{1_w}} < 1$

		<p>carbohydrates are mainly covered through plant-based sources in both forms of diet, the efficiency gain of a plant-based diet only applies to a share of total calories consumed. Taking this into account generates the final intensity factor for a plant-based diet (ID).</p> <p>Since we assume that the biophysical (kcal) and monetary (€) output of the agricultural sector are proportional, the ID can be applied to calculate the reduced land intensity of a plant-based diet compared to a default (meat-based) case.</p> <p>The policy only applies to land used to produce food products which is only demanded by sector 1.</p>	$ID = ID_{pro} * \left(\frac{kcal_{fat+protein}}{kcal_{total}} \right) + 1 - \left(\frac{kcal_{fat+protein}}{kcal_{total}} \right)$ $\frac{land}{kcal} = \frac{land}{\alpha * x}$ $\frac{Foodland}{x_1} = ID * \frac{Foodland_1}{x_1 \quad exog}$
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Table 2: Scenario implementation in MORDRED.

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